

A New Perspective on Physics Through Scale Dimension - A Thought Experiment

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Introduction

This proposal is a thought experiment in physics. While we typically consider time and space as fundamental dimensions in physics, how would our view of physics change if we introduced "scale" itself as a fundamental dimension?

Basic Concept

Modern physics consists of different theoretical frameworks: quantum mechanics, classical physics, and relativity theory. While each brilliantly explains its respective domain, we have not yet achieved a unified understanding.

What I propose is viewing "scale" as a new physical dimension. From this perspective:

1. Physical laws might be expressed as functions of scale
2. It may become possible to mathematically handle transitions between different scales
3. The transition from quantum to classical domains might be describable as a continuous process

Specific Ideas

Introduction of Scale Integration

I am considering expressing physical laws in the following form:

$$\int [s_{\min} \rightarrow s_{\max}] F(x^{\mu}, s) ds = 0$$

Here, $s_{\min}$ represents the Planck scale (quantum domain), and $s_{\max}$ represents the cosmological scale (classical domain). This expression suggests the possibility of treating physical laws uniformly across different scales.

Scale Transitions

For expressing transitions between scales, I consider a function of the form:

$$T(s) = \exp(-|s - s_c| / \lambda)$$

This might be able to express smooth transitions from quantum to classical domains.

Possibilities for Verification

Initial examination of this idea might be possible through:

1. Computer simulation numerical experiments
2. Equation exploration using machine learning
3. Verification of consistency with known physical phenomena

Points for Discussion

I particularly hope to discuss the following points with physics experts:

1. Whether introducing such a scale dimension is physically meaningful
2. How to understand its relationship with existing physical theories
3. Whether there are possibilities for developing this idea further

Conclusion

While this is not yet a complete theory but rather a proposal as a thought experiment, I believe it may offer a new perspective on physics. I hope to deepen these ideas through dialogue with those who find this concept interesting.